

Business Performance Of Small And Micro Community Enterprise In Agricultural Products For Developing The Commercial Quality

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 14, 2021

Accepted:
June 18, 2021

Keywords :

Agriculture Enterprises,
Product Management,
Innovation Management,
Digital Marketing,
Human Capital
Management, Business
Performance

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4990650

Abstract

The objective of this study is to examine the role of resources management in business performance of agriculture enterprises. The relationship between product management, innovation management, digital marketing, human capital management and business performance was examined. Questionnaire was used for data collection and distributed among the employees of agriculture enterprises. Results of the study shows that; product management has positive effect on management of human capital and business performance. Innovation management also has positive effect on human capital and business performance. Finally, digital marketing has positive effect on management of human capital and business performance. Therefore, the current study has vital importance for the practitioners. Thus, the practitioners can promote business performance of agriculture companies with the help of product management, innovation management, digital marketing and human capital management. Agriculture companies should promote product management, innovation management and digital marketing to promote human capital and business performance.

Introduction

Agriculture sector is an important sector among nations. Most of the countries majorly based on the agriculture sector because it has significant importance for the economy. In various countries, agriculture industry play an important role to contribute in the economic development of the country by enhancing the gross-domestic product (GDP). In this direction, Thailand is also one of the countries having great potential for agriculture. Thailand is an agriculture country producing several agriculture products (Kajina, Rousset, Chen, Sornpitak, & Commandré, 2018; Pigg, Richardson, Roberts, & Stair, 2020).

In Thailand agriculture industry, the role of agriculture enterprises is most crucial. Agriculture enterprises support the agriculture activities which increases the output. However, a significant level of business performance is required for these enterprises. The business performance of agriculture enterprises is most important to enhance the overall business performance of agriculture sector in Thailand. Several previous studies also highlighted that business performance of agriculture industry is most crucial (Peter, Rastislav, & Kravcakova, 2017; Rajabion, Khorraminia, Andjomshoaa, Ghafouri-Azar, & Molavi, 2019).

The business performance of the agriculture enterprise is influenced by various factors which include; product management, innovation management and digital marketing. These three factors have major importance in the agriculture sector to promote business performance. Generally, product innovation has positive role in human capital development. It has positive effect on the management of human capital which lead to the business performance. Along with this, innovation cannot be neglected which always play a vital role in business activities. Therefore, it also plays important role to enhance human capital which lead to the business performance. Lastly, the role of digital marketing is vital for business performance as given in literature (Saura, Reyes-Menendez, & Palos-Sanchez, 2020). Therefore, objective of this study is to examine the role of resources management in business performance of agriculture enterprises. The relationship between product management, innovation management, digital marketing, human capital management and business performance was examined. Several previous studies have examined the agriculture sector business performance in different contexts; however, previous studies have not examined the business performance of agriculture enterprises. That is the reason, this study has key contribution to the literature in the filed of agriculture. The relationship examined in this study is first time discussed in relation to the Thai agriculture sector.

2. Literature Review

Agricultural enterprises include those small businesses that involved in the production of food as well as fiber, ranching, and raising of livestock, aquaculture, and all other agricultural related industries. These enterprises can

be described as an institutional unit in its volume as a producer of different agricultural goods and services with independence in respect of financial as well as investment decision making, authority and responsibility for assigning resources for the production of agricultural goods along with the services. These agriculture enterprises have major importance in the business activities (Kopishynska, Utkin, Voloshko, Sliusar, & Kartashova, 2018; Xu, Li, Wu, & Zhang, 2021).

Particularly, these enterprises have major importance for the agriculture nations. The nations depending on the agriculture, generally have major focus on the agriculture enterprises. As these enterprises has major role to play in economy. In agriculture countries, these enterprises produce a huge amount of GDP. It contributes significantly to the economic development of any country based on the agriculture. In most of the countries, agriculture is the backbone of economy (Harman, 2019) because the revenue generated from the agriculture in from of crops help the country to enhance the GDP by creating livelihood opportunities. Therefore, agriculture is one of the most important area in various countries which has important in the economic development. Thailand is one of the countries which contribute to the agriculture filed, these agriculture enterprises are also important for Thailand.

In Thailand, agriculture enterprises also have important role. The agriculture sector of Thailand is also growing which is contributing significantly to the nation's economy. It has important role to generate income for the families and generate various employment opportunities. Therefore, growing agriculture sector of Thailand require agriculture enterprises. Consequently, agriculture enterprises has important role in Thailand (Kaufman & Watanasak, 2011). Number of enterprises in Thailand are increasing as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Agriculture Enterprises in Thailand (2017-2018)

The business performance of these enterprises is most important. Higher performance of enterprises leads to the higher business growth in agriculture. As these enterprises has important role in agriculture sector of Thailand. Therefore, it is most important to enhance the business performance of agriculture enterprises. According to the current study, there are various factors which can enhance the performance of these enterprises. First, products of the agriculture always have major importance for growth. As the better product has the ability to enhance the agriculture output. Therefore, agriculture product management is most crucial to enhance the business performance. Product management is an organizational function within a firm dealing with new product development, business validation, planning, verification, projecting, pricing, product launch, and marketing of a product or products at all stages of the product lifecycle.

Along with the agriculture, in various other enterprises, the role product management is most important in business performance (Igbini, Fandi, Muller, Svec, & Tlusty, 2017; Kumar, Ramanan, & Keelath, 2020). Therefore, importance of product management in agriculture enterprises cannot be neglected as it is the basis of growth of these enterprises in business. Product management generally have important role in human capital (HC) management. The strong relationship between HC management and product management lead to the business performance. Product management generally have positive effect on business performance through HC management. The positive influence of product management on HC management has the ability to promote

business performance. Several previous studies have investigated that product management is most important among the organizations (de Moraes, Vieira, Bagno, & Freitas, 2020; Omrani, Jafari, & Mansori, 2019). Hence, from the above discussion, it is evidence that; product management, HC capital and business performance has important relationship. According to the previous studies, product management has positive role to promote HC management which further lead to the higher business performance. Thus, following hypotheses are proposed;

Hypothesis 1. Product management has positive effect on HC management.

Hypothesis 2. Product management has positive effect on business performance.

Moreover, innovation always play an important role in business performance. Innovation is the generation of new idea which lead to the higher productivity at reduced cost. Management of new ideas is always key to the success for any business activity. As highlighted by the previous studies that innovation has major role to play among business activities (Evans et al., 2017; Hafiz & Sary, 2020). Therefore, management of innovation has key importance for the business activities. Innovation management is simply the procedure of coming up with and presenting new things and emerging the business, one way or the other. It is a mixture of the management of innovation procedures, and change management. It denotes to product, business procedure, marketing as well as organizational innovation. It always has major potential for the business activities. Generally, it has the ability to foster business activities.

Along with the direct effect of innovation management on business performance, it also has indirect effect through HC management. Innovation management and HC management has important relationship with each other's which has importance for the business performance. Particularly, it has important role in agriculture enterprises business performance. As the relationship between HC and innovation is already highlighted in the literature by previous studies (Manev, Gyoshev, & Manolova, 2005; Michaelis & Markham, 2017). Innovation management has positive role to influence HC management which further lead to the higher business performance. Increase in the level of innovation among the agriculture companies, increases the quality of product as well as services which is the basic requirement of higher performance. Therefore, directly and indirectly, innovation management has most important role to promote business performance which lead to the following hypotheses;

Hypothesis 3. Innovation management has positive effect on HC management.

Hypothesis 4. Innovation management has positive effect on business performance.

Furthermore, the third important factor which has influence on business performance of agriculture enterprises is digital marketing. Digital marketing is the element of marketing that uses internet and online based digital technologies such as desktop computers, mobile phones and other digital media as well as platforms to encourage products and services. Marketing itself is always most important for any business activity. Marketing increases the awareness among people which lead to the increases in intention of the people towards specific product. Recently, the digital marketing is emerging among the business activities. Digital marketing is quite easy and less time taking which lead to the higher output. The importance of digital marketing is highlighted by the previous studies (Lee & Falahat, 2019; Marchand, Hennig-Thurau, & Wiertz, 2017).

Digital marketing has important relationship with human capital. HC management is influenced by the digital marketing. As the expertise are required to enhance business activities by using digital marketing. Various companies are using traditional marketing methods which are not well suitable due to the lack in technology adaptability and not having the proper expertise. Therefore, to get higher benefits from marketing activities, digital marketing is most important which required higher level of human capital. Digital marketing has positive role in HC management and HC management further lead to the business performance. As the relationship between marketing and human capital is already highlighted in literature (Chou, Horng, Liu, Huang, & Zhang, 2020; Yatsiuk, 2021). Finally, the following hypotheses are proposed;

Hypothesis 5. HC management has positive effect on business performance.

Hypothesis 6. Digital marketing has positive effect on HC management.

Hypothesis 7. Digital marketing has positive effect on business performance.

3. Methodology

In the current study, to examine the relationship between product management, innovation management, digital marketing, human capital management and business performance, a questionnaire was designed. Questionnaires were designed with the help of previous studies. The scale items of product management, innovation management, digital marketing, human capital management and business performance was adopted from previous studies. Therefore, data were collected with the help of data collection questionnaire which is one of the most suitable way (Bowling, Bond, Jenkinson, & Lamping, 1999). Thus, the current study used quantitative research approach in which firsthand data were collected.

Data collected was performed with the help of area cluster sampling which is most suitable in the current study. Various previous studies collected the data with the help of area cluster sampling which is most suitable technique to cover the maximum population as mentioned by the previous studies (WU Hameed, 2019; Johnson, Baburajan, & Sulekha, 2020). While collecting the data by using cluster sampling, whole population was divided into various clusters. After making different clusters, data were collected with the help of random

selection. Few clusters were selected randomly for data collection. 600 questionnaires were distributed for data collection. From total questionnaires, only 190 questionnaires were received from the respondents and used for data analysis.

4. Results

The results of this study are based on the structural equation modeling (SEM) which is recommended in several previous studies (J. Hair, Hollingsworth, Randolph, & Chong, 2017; J. F. Hair, Sarstedt, Pieper, & Ringle, 2012; W. U. Hameed, Mohammad, & Shahar, 2020), as it is one of the most popular technique for data analysis. To test the hypotheses based on the primary data, SEM is widely recommended by the previous studies. Hence, this study used SEM to examine the relationship between variables. Before to use SEM, this study examined the data statistics as given in Table 1. Table 1 shows that minimum and maximum value which shows the outlier in the data. As it is most important to fix the errors related to the outlier because outlier may change the original results. Therefore, to ensure the maximum originality of the data, all the errors related to the outlier was fixed. Furthermore, this study identified all the missing values (Aydin & ŞENOĞLU, 2018; Yang et al., 2020). As availability of missing value in the data may cause negative effect on the results. Finally, while examining the preliminary data analysis, this study also examined the normality of the data. The last two columns of the Table 1 show the values for normality. It is found that data is normal and accurate to proceed further.

Table 1. Statistical test of empirical variables (n=340)

Variable	Range	Min	Max	\bar{X}	SD.	Variance	SK	KU
Production Management(PRM)								
PM1	3.33	1.67	5.00	4.22	0.74	0.54	-0.95	0.58
PM2	3.50	1.50	5.00	4.22	0.72	0.51	-0.99	1.15
PM3	3.50	1.50	5.00	4.21	0.74	0.55	-1.00	0.79
Innovative Management(INM)								
IM1	3.00	2.00	5.00	3.57	0.74	0.55	0.33	-0.48
IM2	3.00	2.00	5.00	3.69	0.76	0.58	-0.15	-0.51
IM3	3.00	2.00	5.00	3.74	0.74	0.55	-0.04	-0.65
Digital Marketing (DIM)								
DM1	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.19	0.81	0.66	-0.84	0.03
DM2	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.13	0.79	0.62	-0.75	0.00
DM3	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.17	0.76	0.57	-0.85	0.37
Human Capital Management								
HCM1	3.60	1.40	5.00	3.98	0.79	0.62	-0.69	-0.07
HCM2	3.75	1.25	5.00	4.05	0.79	0.62	-0.73	0.09
HCM3	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.14	0.79	0.62	-0.72	-0.09
HCM4	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.19	0.73	0.54	-0.78	-0.03
HCM5	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.21	0.75	0.56	-0.76	-0.14
Business Performance (BUP)								
BP1	3.50	1.50	5.00	4.17	0.78	0.62	-0.95	0.32
BP2	3.50	1.50	5.00	4.17	0.78	0.60	-1.00	0.58
BP3	3.00	2.00	5.00	4.09	0.84	0.70	-0.62	-0.53

Note: PRM = Product Management; INM = Innovation Management; DIM = Digital Marketing; HCM = Human Capital Management; BP = Business Performance

Furthermore, this study examined the factor loadings to confirm the reliability of the data. Reliability was confirmed the insuring the factor loadings above 0.5 for all scale items. Figure 2 shows that product management is measured with the help of three scale items and all the items have factor loadings above 0.5. Along with this, innovation management is measured with the help of three scale items and none of the item is below 0.5 factor loadings. Digital marketing is measured by using three scale items and all the items have factor loadings above 0.5. Human capital management is measured by using five scale items are all items have achieved the minimum level of factor loadings. Finally, business performance is measured by using three scale items and none of item was deleted due to low factor loading. Hence, all the scale items have achieved the minimum threshold level which achieved the internal item consistency. According to previous studies, composite reliability should be above 0.7 (F. Hair Jr, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & G. Kuppelwieser, 2014; J. F. Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2013; Hair Jr, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2016). Results in Table 2 highlighted that; product management, innovation management, digital marketing, human capital management and business performance has composite reliability above 0.7. Furthermore, to examine the convergent validity, the current study examined average variance extracted (AVE) which is also given in Table 2. AVE must be above 0.5 for all the

variables (Waseem Hameed et al., 2018). According to the results of the current study, all the constructs; product management, innovation management, digital marketing, human capital management and business performance have AVE above 0.5. Standard error was also examined along with the t-value which is given in Table 2.

Table 2 Factor Loadings. (n = 340)

Variable	λ	SE.	t-value	R ²	AVE	CR.
Products Management(PRM)					0.764	0.905
PM1 (Parameter constants)	0.95	-	-	91.0%		
PM2	0.71	0.041	17.475**	48.0%		
PM3	0.94	0.032	31.133**	99.0%		
Innovative Management (INM)					0.735	0.891
IM1(Parameter constants)	0.70	-	-	88.0%		
IM2	0.94	0.089	15.634**	89.0%		
IM3	0.92	0.084	15.741**	89.0%		
Digital Marketing(DIM)					0.942	0.980
DM1 (Parameter constants)	0.95	-	-	98.0%		
DM2	0.98	0.021	47.108**	85.0%		
DM3	0.98	0.02	47.221**	96.0%		
Human Capital Management(HCM)					0.940	0.987
HCM1 (Parameter constants)	0.94	-	-	90.0%		
HCM2	0.95	0.028	36.594**	84.0%		
HCM3	0.97	0.033	31.883**	50.0%		
HCM4	0.99	0.037	26.723**	95.0%		
HCM5	0.99	0.04	25.057**	93.0%		
Business Performance (BUP)					0.913	0.969
BP1 (Parameter constants)	0.97	-	-	96.0%		
BP2	0.98	0.019	53.663**	90.0%		
BP3	0.92	0.029	34.640**	97.0%		

Note: PRM = Product Management; INM = Innovation Management; DIM = Digital Marketing; HCM = Human Capital Management; BP = Business Performance

After the assessment of reliability and validity. The current study examined the relationship between variables. This study proposed seven hypotheses which are test in this section. Therefore, Figure 2 shows the relationship between product management, innovation management, digital marketing, human capital management and business performance. The effect of product management was examined on HC management and business performance. The effect of innovation management was examined on HC management and business performance. Furthermore, the effect of digital marketing was examined on HC management and business performance. Finally, this section also examined the effect of HC management and business performance. All these relationships was examined by using SEM which most recommended technique in the literature (Waseem Hameed & Naveed, 2019; Henseler & Chin, 2010; Henseler et al., 2014). The process of SEM is given in Figure 1 and results are given in Table 3.

Note: PRM = Product Management; INM = Innovation Management; DIM = Digital Marketing; HCM = Human Capital Management; BP = Business Performance

Figure 6. Structural Equation Modeling of Resource management affecting business performance of agricultural products community enterprises (n = 340)

According to the results given in Table 3, all the hypotheses are supported. To examine the relationship between variables, t-value 1.96 was considered a minimum threshold level for significance. Furthermore, the beta value was examined to check the direction of the relationship. It is found that; product management has significant effect on HC management with t-value 5.479. Product management also has significant relationship with business performance as the t-value is 3.9. Innovation management has positive and significant relationship with HC management with t-value 9.012. It also has positive effect on business performance with t-value 2.536. It is also found that; the relationship between digital marketing and HC management is significant with t-value 5.174. Digital marketing also has positive effect on business performance with t-value 1.983. Finally, a positive and significant relationship was found between HC management and business performance with t-value 2.224. Furthermore, Table 3 shows the r-square value which is acceptable. It shows that all the variables; product management, innovation management, digital marketing and HC management is expected to bring significant change in business performance. Additionally, Table 4 also shows the effect of each independent variable on dependent variable which is also acceptable.

Table 3. Results

	Variable	β	SE.	t-value	Sig.	R ²
HCM	<-- INM	0.55	0.08	9.012	0.000**	81.0%
HCM	<-- PRM	0.40	0.07	5.479	0.000**	81.0%
HCM	<-- DIM	0.36	0.06	5.174	0.000**	81.0%
BUP	<-- INM	0.33	0.20	2.536	0.011*	99.0%
BUP	<-- DIM	0.17	0.08	1.983	0.047*	99.0%
BUP	<-- HCM	0.42	0.22	2.224	0.026*	99.0%
BUP	<-- PRM	0.36	0.10	3.900	0.000**	99.0%

Note: PRM = Product Management; INM = Innovation Management; DIM = Digital Marketing; HCM = Human Capital Management; BP = Business Performance

Table 4 Result of testing for SEM influences (n = 340)

Variable	effect	Human Capital Management	Business Performance
Product Management	DE	0.40	0.36
	IE	-	0.17
	TE	0.40	0.53
Innovative Management	DE	0.55	0.33
	IE	-	0.23
	TE	0.55	0.56
Digital Marketing	DE	0.36	0.17
	IE	-	0.15
	TE	0.36	0.32
Human Capital Management	DE	N/A	0.42
	IE	N/A	-
	TE	N/A	0.42
R ²		81.0%	99.0%

**DE=direct effect; IE=indirect effect; TE=Total effect

5. Conclusion

This study examines the relationship between product management, innovation management, digital marketing, HC management and business performance. To examine this relationship, quantitative research was preferred in which a survey was performed to collect data. Data were gathered from various agriculture companies with the help of questionnaires. Finally, results were obtained with the help of statistical software. Results of the study revealed that; product management has positive effect on HC management. It shows the increase in HC management increases the business performance. Furthermore, innovation management is also an important factor which contribute to business performance. It has positive effect on HC management and business performance. Increase in innovation management increases the HC management and business performance. Along with the product management and innovation management, digital marketing also play an important role to enhance the HC management. Increase in digital marketing increases the HC management. Similarly, increase in digital marketing increases the business performance. Therefore, product management, innovation management and digital marketing has positive role to enhance HC management which further lead to the business performance. Therefore, it is really important for the agriculture companies to enhance business performance with the help of HC management and HC management can be promoted through product management, innovation management has digital marketing.

6. Implications of the Study

The current study has major importance for literature as well as practice. Theoretically, this is unique study as it examined the relationship between product management, innovation management, digital marketing, HC management and business performance. These are one of the unique relationships as this relationship is not examined among the agriculture companies of Thailand. This relationship is not considered by the previous studies in the literature. Therefore, theoretically, this study has important contribution to the literature. Practically, the current study also provides several insights for the agriculture companies of Thailand to enhance the business performance. According to the current study human capital is most important to enhance business performance. Therefore, agriculture companies of Thailand should promote human capital. Additionally, this study proved that product management, innovation management and digital marketing is most important for human management and business performance. Therefore, agriculture companies should promote product management, innovation management and digital marketing to promote human capital and business performance. Hence, the practitioners can promote business performance of agriculture companies with the help of product management, innovation management, digital marketing and human capital management.

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